

A STUDY OF OPTIMUM CONDITIONS IN THE SYNTHESIS OF 2': 3: 4'-TRIHYROXYCHALKONE AND 2': 4: 4'- TRIHYROXY-3-METHOXYCHALKONE

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A critical study of the factors influencing the yield of two representative hydroxychalkones, prepared by the Claisen-Schmidt condensation, has been made.

In continuation of the previous work on chalkones (Dhar and Lal, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 1159), it was felt of interest to study the effect of several factors, e.g., reaction time, temperature and solvent, on the yield of some hydroxychalkones. Two chalkones, viz., 2': 3: 4'-trihydroxychalkone and 2': 4: 4'-trihydroxy-3-methoxychalkone, were chosen as the model compounds.

2': 3: 4'-Trihydroxychalkone was prepared by the Claisen-Schmidt reaction according to the procedure of Kostanecki and Rossbach (*Ber.*, 1896, **29**, 1488). The chalkone crystallised from a mixture of benzene-ethanol in yellow microneedles, m.p. 216-17° (uncorr.) (Tambor, *Ber.*, 1916, **49**, 1704, reported m.p. 209°). A mixture of 2': 3: 4'-trihydroxychalkone and 3': 7-dihydroxyflavanone resulted when the above condensation was carried out at 50-55° for 24 hours (8 hours per day for 3 days).

2': 4: 4'-Trihydroxy-3-methoxychalkone was prepared as described previously (Dhar and Lal, *loc. cit.*).

The yields of the above chalkones under different experimental conditions † are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I
2': 3: 4'-Trihydroxychalkone.

Resacetophenone=1 g. *m*-Hydroxybenzaldehyde=0.8 g.

Expt. No.	Solvent (12.5 c.c.)	Condensing agent.	Condensed for.	Yield of chalkone**	
1.	Ethanol	KOH/H ₂ O (5g./5 c.c.)	2 hrs.	0.35 g.	20.8%
2.	Do	Do	4	0.48	21.6
3.	Methanol	Do	2	0.24	14.3
4.	Ethylene glycol	Do	..	0.53	31.5
5.	Ethylene glycol-water (1:1)	Do	..	0.65	38.7
6.	Water	Do	..	0.67	39.9
7.	Ethanol	NaOH/H ₂ O (5g./5c.c.)	..	0.10	5.9
8.	Do	NaOEt/EtOH Na (2g.) in ethanol (28.6c.c.)	}	..	..
9.	Methanol	NaOMe/MeOH Na (2g.) in methanol (28.6c.c.)		..	..
10.	Ethanol	KOH/H ₂ O (5g./5 c.c.)	..	0.56	33.3
11.	Do	..	24 (at room temp.)	0.46	27.3
12.	Do	.. (5g./15 c.c.)	2	0.18	10.7
13.	..	.. (10g./17.5 c.c.)	..	0.32	19.0
14.	..	.. (10g./8.8 c.c.)	..	0.10	5.9

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** The yield has been calculated on the weight of the chalkone melting at 209-13°.

† All the experiments were carried out at 60° unless otherwise stated.

TABLE II

2' : 4 : 4'-Trihydroxy-3-methoxychalkone.

Resacetophenone=5 g. Vanillin=5 g.

Expt. No.	KOH/H ₂ O. (g./c.c.)	MeOH	Ethylene glycol	Initial temp. to start reaction.	Duration of heating.	Condensed for.	Yield of chalkone.
1.	88/140	..	..	..	..	9 days	0.79 g. 8.4%
2.	..	..	..	60-65°	32 mins.	8 ..	1.75 18.6
3.	47.5%	..	..	..	..	6 weeks	2.82 30.8
4.	88/140	60 c.c.	..	..	..	7 days	0.58 6.2
5.	"	"	..	..	..	4 weeks	1.97 21.0
6.	47.5%	..	..	..	..	6 ..	1.28 13.8
7.	88/140	..	60 c.c.	95°	1.5 hrs.	8 days	1.72 18.3
8.	"	..	"	..	..	Do	0.95 10.1
9.	47.5%	..	"	..	..	6 weeks	1.14 12.1
10.	88/140	100	..	..	..	1 week	0.50 5.4
11.	"	80	..	95°	20 mins.	24 hrs.	0.44 4.9

Examination of Table I indicates the following :

(i) *Reaction time* : The yield of the chalkone increases on increasing the reaction period from 2 to 4 hours (cf. Expt. 1 and 2).

(ii) *Solvent* : Using different solvents as reaction medium, the yield of the chalkone varies in the order : water > ethylene glycol-water > ethylene glycol > ethanol > methanol (cf. Expt. 1, 3, 4, 5 and 6).

(iii) *Condensing agent* : Aqueous potassium hydroxide is preferable to sodium hydroxide, as the use of the latter affords the chalkone of low purity and in a poor yield (cf. Expt. 1, 7, 8 and 9).

(iv) *Concentration of the condensing agent* : Increasing the concentration of the condensing agent, up to a certain limit, results in increase in the yield of the chalkone and *vice versa* (cf. Expt. 7 and 12; 13 and 14).

(v) *Effect of using excess m-hydroxybenzaldehyde* : The use of the aldehyde in excess than the stoichiometric proportion in the Claisen-Schmidt reaction results in an increase in the yield of the chalkone (cf. Expt. 1 and 10).

(vi) *Temperature* : Higher temperature exerts a favourable influence in bringing about the reaction in a relatively short time. However, no significant difference in the yield of the chalkone is apparent when the reaction is conducted at room temperature for a prolonged period (cf. Expt. 2 and 11).

Examination of Table II indicates the following :

(1) *Solvent* : Ethanol does not appear to be a good reaction medium in this condensation as the chalkone invariably separates as an oil, which is difficult to crystallise. Ethylene glycol and

water, however, are suitable as solvents (cf. Expt. 1, 2, 7 and 8); but the use of the latter is advantageous when the reaction is carried out over a prolonged period (cf. Expt. 3, 6 and 9).

(2) *Reaction time* : The yield of the chalkone appears to increase by increasing the period of condensation (cf. Expt. 3, 4 and 5).

(3) *Temperature* : In the foregoing condensation, involving the use of ethylene glycol or water as a reaction medium, the initial heating of the reaction mixture for a short time results in increase in the yield of the chalkone (cf. Expt. 2 and 7).

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